

The burden of glaucoma in a tertiary hospital, Jos, Plateau State, North Central Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Global glaucoma prevalence is projected to reach 111 million by 2040. In Nigeria, it remains the primary cause of irreversible blindness. Late presentation is often driven by the disease's asymptomatic, gradual onset, coupled with low public awareness and financial constraints. This study assessed the clinical presentation and management of glaucoma patients at a tertiary eye clinic. A retrospective, hospital-based descriptive study was conducted on 446 patients newly diagnosed with glaucoma between 2018 and 2019. The mean age of participants was 55.9 years, with a male-to-female ratio of approximately 1.5:1 (59.6% male). Patients over age 40 comprised 79.8% of the cohort. Alarming, 17.5% presented with bilateral blindness, and 35.2% of all eyes were blind at first presentation. Primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) was the predominant type (89.9%), followed by glaucoma suspects (5.6%), secondary glaucoma (2.7%), and primary angle-closure glaucoma (1.8%). Severe structural damage was evident, with 58.7% of eyes showing a vertical cup-to-disc ratio (VCDR) 0.9, and 22.6% exhibiting VCDR asymmetry 0.2. Regarding management, 94.6% opted for medical therapy while only 1.5% underwent surgery. Beta-blockers (73.7%) and prostaglandin analogues (18.4%) were the primary medications prescribed. The study highlights a significant glaucoma burden characterized by advanced disease at presentation and a high prevalence of POAG. The findings underscore an urgent need for public enlightenment and subsidized screening programs to facilitate early detection and prevention of irreversible vision loss.

Keywords: Glaucoma, late presentation, medical management

INTRODUCTION

Glaucoma is a group of ocular disorders with multifactorial aetiology, united by a characteristic optic neuropathy. It is associated with potentially progressive, clinically visible changes at the optic nerve head (ONH), including focal or generalized thinning of the neuroretinal rim, excavation, and enlargement of the optic cup. These changes reflect neurodegeneration of

retinal ganglion cell axons and deformation of the lamina cribrosa. There is a corresponding diffuse and/or localized nerve fibre bundle defect, resulting in characteristic visual field loss. However, these defects may not be detectable in the early stages with most visual field analysers. The pattern of visual field loss depends on the stage at presentation. Intraocular pressure (IOP) is often elevated above 21 mmHg, but it may also remain within the normal range (≤ 21 mmHg).

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Reduction of IOP remains the only currently known modifiable risk factor in the management of glaucoma. Visual acuity is typically preserved in the early stages, but disease progression can eventually lead to complete loss of vision. Late presentation is common and is often driven by the asymptomatic and gradual onset of the disease, as well as low public awareness and financial constraints.

There is an estimate of about 111 million people who will be affected by glaucoma by 2040, worldwide, and with a higher burden in Africa and Asia^(1,2) Globally, about 8.4 million people are blind from glaucoma. About 15% of the blindness in Africa results from glaucoma, and 16.7% of blindness in Nigeria was attributed to glaucoma in the national blindness and visual impairment study.^(3,4) In Nigeria, it is the second cause of blindness, and a leading cause of irreversible blindness.⁽³⁾ Primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) has been identified as the most common type of glaucoma, especially among Africans.^(2,7,8) In Africa and people of African ancestry, it starts earlier in life and pursues a more aggressive course leading to blindness, compared to the Caucasians.⁽⁹⁻¹¹⁾ This reflects multifactorial influences, including greater genetic susceptibility with optineurin (OPTN), myocilin (MYOC), and TANK-binding kinase 1 (TBK1), anatomical differences (larger optic discs, thinner corneas), and increased retinal ganglion cell vulnerability⁽¹²⁻¹⁷⁾. Earlier onset, often 10–20 years earlier, leads to longer disease duration and cumulative damage. Combined with later presentation, vascular and environmental factors, and healthcare access limitations; contribute to more advanced disease at diagnosis and poorer outcomes. Lack of awareness and knowledge about the disease, and extreme financial constrain, are attributable factors for late presentation at eye care health facilities in the advanced stage of the disease.^(10,11,18-25) Globally, glaucoma predominantly affects people in the lower socioeconomic class disproportionately.

This study evaluates the burden, clinical presentation, and management modalities for glaucoma in an eye clinic at a tertiary care hospital in North Central Nigeria. By providing the first region-specific data in this

population, it fills a critical knowledge gap and offers evidence to inform policy, improve early detection strategies, and strengthen glaucoma care services.

METHODOLOGY

This is a hospital-based descriptive retrospective study of patients who were diagnosed with glaucoma on the first presentation at the eye clinic of Bingham University Teaching Hospital (BHUTH), Jos between January 2018 and December 2019, inclusive. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee (Approval No : NHREC/21/05/2005/00921).

Patient confidentiality was strictly maintained by anonymizing all data using hospital numbers, initials, gender, and ethnicity, with no identifying personal information disclosed. All information collected was handled securely and used solely for the purpose of improving patient care and management.

Records with complete and relevant information required for the study were included, while records with incomplete or missing data were excluded from the analysis.

Patients' sociodemographic and personal data such as age, gender, ethnicity, and occupation were retrieved from their hospital records. History of glaucoma in self and family members, recorded presenting visual acuity and best-corrected visual acuity for each eye and both eyes, ocular examination, investigations, diagnosis, and treatment planned or offered, received, or declined where available, were retrieved from the records.

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel (*Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA, USA*) and analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, version 23.0 (*IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA*)

Continuous variables such as age were summarized as mean \pm standard deviation, while categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages.

Vertical cup-to-disc ratio (VCDR) was recorded for both eyes. For analyses involving a single eye per participant, the eye with the lower (better) VCDR was selected. Disc asymmetry was summarized using mean \pm standard

deviation and frequency distribution.

Treatment modalities and antiglaucoma medications were presented as frequencies and percentages. Associations between categorical variables were evaluated using Pearson's Chi-square test, with statistical significance set at $p \leq 0.05$.

The relationships between age group and gender at presentation, VCDR and presenting visual acuity, and VCDR and glaucoma subtype were assessed using cross-tabulation and Pearson's Chi-square test. Similarly, the association between treatment modalities and age, gender, and presenting visual acuity was evaluated using the same method.

RESULTS

There were 446 consecutive new patients with the diagnosis of glaucoma during the study period.

Their ages ranged from 12 to 107 years with a mean of 55.9 (std. ± 37.65) years. Male to female ratio was 1.5:1. The highest proportion of patients, 214 (47.9%), presented in the fifth and sixth decades of life and those above 40 years of age were 356 (79.8%) [Table 1].

Seventy-eight (17.5%) patients presented blind in both eyes, and 314 (35.2%) eyes were blind (VA $< 3/60$) at presentation [Table 2]. There were a further 329 (36.9%) eyes with a visual acuity of $< 6/60$. The various subtypes of glaucoma are presented in Figure 1. More individuals presented with POAG, 401 (89.9%). About 25 (5.6%) individuals were glaucoma suspects. Primary angle-closure glaucoma (PACG) was seen in only 8 (1.8%) patients. The secondary glaucoma was present in 12 (2.7%) patients. These were due to trauma in eight patients, intumescent cataract in two patients, and there was one case each of retinal detachment with rubeosis and couching. Two hundred and seventy-eight (62.3%) patients had severe/advanced to end-stage optic neuropathy with VCDR ≥ 0.9 in the right eye, 298 (66.8%) in the left eye, and 226 (50.7%) bilaterally. The mean VCDR was 0.87 (std ± 0.125) and 0.88 (std ± 0.122) for the right and left eyes, respectively. Most of the patients, 212 (47.5%), with POAG had VCDR > 0.85 , whereas most of the glaucoma suspects, 24 (5.4%), had VCDR $< 0.6-0.7$, [Table 3]. Up to 345

(77.4%) patients had VCDR asymmetry of < 0.2 and 101 (22.6%) of ≥ 0.2 [Table 4]. Significant number of the patients, 168 (37.7%), with VCDR > 0.85 had a moderate visual impairment to blindness ($P < 0.000$) [Table 5].

Most of the patients, 422 (94.6%), made a choice for medical treatment rather than surgery. Only 7 (1.5%) patients opted for and had surgery five combined procedure (cataract surgery and trabeculectomy) and two trabeculectomy only.

Beta-blockers were used in 329 (73.7%) patients, prostaglandin analogues in 82 (18.4%), and pilocarpine in 6 (3.6%). An additional 8 (1.8%) patients required acetazolamide to further reduce intraocular pressure (IOP). Mild-to-moderate allergic reactions occurred in 16 (1.3%) patients, necessitating antiallergic medications [Table 6]; however, discontinuation of antiglaucoma therapy was not required.

Treatment options stratified by age, gender, and presenting visual acuity are shown in Table 7.

Tables and Figures for The Burden of Glaucoma in a Tertiary Hospital...

Table 1 : Sociodemographic disposition of 446 patients.

Age groups (years)	Gender		Total, n(%)
	Male, n(%)	Female, n(%)	
11 to 20	4(0.9)	10(2.2)	14(3.1)
21-30	12(2.7)	15(3.4)	27(6.1)
31-40	26(5.8)	23(5.2)	49(11.0)
41-50	34(7.6)	30(6.7)	64(14.3)
51-60	75(16.8)	38(8.5)	113(25.3)
61-70	61(13.7)	40(9.0)	101(22.6)
71-80	45(10.1)	20(4.5)	65(14.6)
>80	9(2.0)	4(.9)	13(2.9)
Total	266(59.6)	180(40.4)	446(100)
$P=0.32$			

Figure 1: Glaucoma subtypes in 446 glaucoma patients.

Table 2.: The presenting visual acuity in 446 glaucoma patients.

Presenting visual acuity	Right eye, n(%)	Left eye, n(%)	Both eyes, n(%)
NVA >=6/12	126(28.3)	123(27.6)	154(34.5)
MiVI <6/12-6/18	61(13.7)	59(13.2)	93(20.9)
MoVI <6/18-6/60	91(20.4)	103(32.1)	114(25.6)
SVI <6/60-3/60	6(1.3)	9(2.0)	7(1.6)
Blindness <3/60	162(36.3)	152(34.1)	78(17.5)
Total	446(100.0)	446(100.0)	446(100.0)

n: Number of patients; NVA: Normal visual acuity; MiVI: Mild visual impairment; MoVI: Moderate visual impairment; SVI: Severe visual impairment.

Table 3: The vertical cup-to-disc ratio and glaucoma subtype in 446 glaucoma patients

VCDR	Glaucoma subtype				Total
	Open-angle glaucoma n(%)	Angle-closure glaucoma n(%)	Secondary glaucoma n(%)	Glaucoma suspect n(%)	
Mild/early <=0.6-0.7	81(18.2)		0 3(0.7)	24(5.4)	108(24.2)
Moderate >0.7-0.85	108(24.2)	1(0.2)	2(0.4)	1(0.2)	112(25.1)
Severe/advanced >0.85-0.99	138(30.9)		0 5(1.1)		0 143(32.1)
End stage 1.0	74(16.6)	7(1.6)	2(0.4)		0 83(18.6)
Total	401(89.9)	8(1.8)	12(2.7)	25(5.6)	446(100.0)

P=0.000
VCDR: Vertical cup-to-disc ratio.

Table 4: The vertical cup-to-disc ratio and asymmetry in 446 glaucoma patients.

Vertical cup-to-disc ratio	Right eye, n(%)	Left eye, n(%)
Mild/early <=0.6-0.7	70(15.7)	73(16.4)
Moderate >0.7-0.85	97(21.7)	75(16.8)
Severe/advanced >0.85-0.99	112(25.1)	137(30.7)
End stage 1.0	166(37.2)	161(36.1)
Total	446(100.0)	446(100.0)
Mean+-SD	0.87+-0.125	0.88_-0.122
VCDR asymmetry, n(%)		
<0.2	345(77.4)	
>=0.2	101(22.6)	

SD: Standard deviation; VCDR: Vertical cup-to-disc ratio

Table 5: The vertical cup-to-disc ratio and presenting visual acuity both eyes in 446 glaucoma patients.

VCDR	NVA (>=6/12)	MiVI (<6/12-6/18)	MoVI (<6/18-6/60)	SVI (<6/60-3/60)	Blindness (<3/60)	P=0.000
Mild/early <=0.6-0.7	93(20.9)	12(2.7)	2(0.4)		0 1(0.2)	108(24.2)
Moderate >0.7-0.85	53(11.9)	31(7.0)	27(6.1)		0 1(0.2)	112(25.1)
Severe/advanced >0.85-0.99	8(1.8)	50(11.2)	85(19.1)		0	0 143(32.1)
End stage 1.0	0	0	0	7(1.6)	76(17.0)	83(18.6)
Total P=0.000	154(34.5)	93(20.9)	114(25.6)	7(1.6)	78(17.5)	446(100.0)

n: Number of patients; NVA: Normal visual acuity; MiVI: Mild visual impairment; MoVI: Moderate visual impairment; SVI: Severe visual impairment; VCDR: Vertical cup-to-disc ratio.

Table 6: Treatment options and medications for 446 patients with glaucoma.

Treatment options	Patients n(%)
Medications only	422(94.6)
Trabeculectomy	2(0.4)
Combined procedure	5(1.1)
Refer	1(0.2)
Counsel for surgery	4(0.9)
Injectio "absolute alcohol"	1(0.2)
Follow-up only	11(2.5)
Total	446(100.0)
Drugs	
BB	329(73.7)
PGAs	82(18.4)
Acetazolamide	8(1.8)
Antiallergic	16(3.6)
Pilocarpine	6(1.3)
Mydriatics	2(0.4)

BB; Beta blockers,PGAs: Prostaglandin analogues.

Table 7: Treatment option based on age, gender, and presenting visual acuity | 446 glaucoma patients.

Treatment option	Age groups (years) P=0.30								Gender P=0.168		Presenting visual acuity both eyes P=0.262				
	11 to 20, n(%)	21 to 30, n(%)	31 to 40, n(%)	41 to 50, n(%)	51 to 60, n(%)	61 to 70, n(%)	71 to 80, n(%)	>80	Male n(%)	Female, n(%)	NVA(<6/12)	MVI(-6/12-6/18)	MoV(<6/18-6/60)	SVI(<6/60-3/60)	Blindness(<3/60)
Medications only	14(3.1)	21(4.7)	43(9.6)	59(13.2)	111(24.9)	99(22.2)	62(13.9)	13(2.9)	25(57.6)	165(37.0)	92(20.0)	108(24.2)	7(1.6)	74(16.6)	422(94.6)
Trabeculectomy	0	1(0.2)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2(0.4)	0	1(0.2)	0	0	2(0.4)
Combined procedure	0	0	2(0.4)	1(0.2)	1(0.2)	0	0	0	0	2(0.4)	3(0.7)	1(0.2)	1(0.2)	0	3(0.7)
Refer	0	0	0	1(0.2)	0	0	0	0	0	1(0.2)	0	0	0	0	1(0.2)
Counsel for surgery	0	2(0.4)	0	1(0.2)	1(0.2)	0	0	0	0	1(0.2)	3(0.7)	0	1(0.2)	0	4(0.9)
injection "absolute alcohol"	0	0	0	0	0	1(0.2)	0	0	0	1(0.2)	1(0.2)	0	0	0	1(0.2)
Follow-up only	0	3(0.7)	4(0.9)	2(0.4)	0	1(0.2)	1(0.2)	0	6(1.3)	5(1.1)	0	3(0.7)	0	0	11(2.5)
Total	14(3.1)	27(6.1)	49(11.0)	64(14.3)	113(25.3)	101(22.5)	65(14.6)	13(2.9)	266(59.6)	180(40.4)	93(21)	114(25.6)	7(1.6)	78(17.5)	446(100.0)

NVA: Normal visual acuity;MVI: Mild visual impairment; MoV: Moderate visual impairment; SVI: Severe visual impairment.

DISCUSSION

This study presented the burden of glaucoma and the challenges of management of new patients at BHUTH eye clinic within the study period. The siting of BHUTH in town centre, in a low-income area, with its competitive billing makes it accessible and affordable, attracting patients located within its immediate vicinity and referrals from other peripheral hospitals within and outside the state.

Almost one-sixth of the patients presented blind in both eyes, and more than one-third of eyes were blind by visual acuity measurement. This is like previous studies in Nigeria and other sub-Saharan African countries in patients with glaucoma presenting blind for the first time to the hospital. A study in Kano mission eye hospital by Bowman and Kirupanathan²⁵⁾ reported that 53% of the eyes were blind at presentation. Omoti et al⁽¹⁰⁾, reported that 24.4% of new patients with glaucoma presented blind. A study in Benue State University Teaching Hospital eye clinic reported 22.3% of blind

eyes at presentation and 11.9% were blind in both eyes.

⁽²⁶⁾ This may be due to lack of awareness and ignorance of the disease which is almost symptomless in the early stage. The glaucoma awareness campaign started after the completion of national blindness and visual impairment study of 2007, when it was shown that glaucoma was the leading cause of irreversible blindness in Nigeria. It is, therefore, hoped that with the increasing campaigns, earlier presentation will become more common in future. Mafwiri et al.⁽²⁷⁾ in Dar-es-Salaam reported that 29% of patients presented blind. In the index study, 35.2% of eyes were blind at presentation.

Most of the patients in the present study were in their fifth and sixth decades of life, and they made up almost half of the individuals with severe or end-stage disease. This is younger than the presentation among the Caucasians, but agrees with previous studies that found glaucoma presenting at an earlier age among Africans and with a more aggressive course.^(9-12,26-31) Most Africans

have a larger optic disc with a larger cup.⁽³¹⁾ The nerve fibre bundles may, therefore, lack tissue support leading to more nerve axonal death.

POAG was the major subtype of glaucoma seen. Worldwide, especially among the patients of African ancestry, POAG is the most common type of glaucoma^(2,7,8) It presents insidiously, bilaterally, is painless, and asymmetrically at the early stage; hence, patients may not be aware that they have the disease until the vision is seriously compromised in one or both eyes before they seek eye care. Hence, more than one-third of the patients presented blind in at least one eye in the present study.

Glaucoma suspects were identified in 5.6% of the patients; some of whom may get lost to follow-up and present later with severe disease. Most instruments such as Octopus, Optopol, and even Humphrey visual field analyser may not pick the visual field damage in suspects using the white-on-white program. A new module of Humphrey visual field analyser with 10-2, especially the 10-2C program, can assess the macular vulnerability zone and pick field defects in such patients, but it is not available in most centres. The absence of ocular coherent tomography (OCT) or no affordability makes follow-up difficult in these patients. The OCT can assess retinal ganglion nerve fibre and cell complex to detect glaucoma at an earlier stage.

A fundus or retinal camera photography is useful in detecting a retinal haemorrhage which may precede a nerve fibre defect that may be useful for surveillance follow-up.

In the absence of the equipment described, the, identification of concerning features is dependent on keen observation of the optic nerve head and detection of nerve fibre defects, optic disc haemorrhage, and disc rim thinning with IOP rise.

Another strategy is the use of topical anti-glaucoma medications in patients with a strong family history of glaucoma, who have raised IOP as this may slow down or stop the progress to glaucoma in some individuals.⁽³²⁾

The presence of PACG was low in our study at 1.8%. Most studies found PACG low among people of African descents. In Ibadan, it was 8.3%⁽³³⁾ and in Benin City

1.7%.^(34,35) A study in Benue State University Teaching Hospital eye clinic reported 2.9%.⁽²⁶⁾ On the other hand, a higher prevalence was reported in an Ethiopian eye clinic 18.5%.⁽³⁶⁾ Whereas it is the most common type of glaucoma in people of Asiatic descent;⁽³⁷⁾ it is not so common among Africans, especially in West Africans compared to East Africa. A proper assessment of anterior chamber angle may rule out some patients with chronic angle-closure glaucoma, who may be managed as open-angle glaucoma.

Although the secondary glaucoma was not found to be high in the present study, it often follows trauma in the work environment. Modifications to ensure safety of staff, including the use of protective goggles in at-risk environments where people are exposed to sharp implements, and provision of adequate security for farmers will reduce this avoidable glaucoma.

More than half of the patients presented with severe/advanced to end-stage optic nerve neuropathy with VCDR ≥ 0.9 bilaterally. This is not surprising; due to late presentation, patients tend to come in at the stage of severe/advanced optic neuropathy. Bowman et al.⁽²⁵⁾ in Kano reported 63% of eyes with VCDR of >0.8 , and Mafwiri et al.⁽²⁷⁾ in Dar-es Salaam reported 70%. Almost half of the patients with POAG had VCDR >0.85 , whereas one in 20 of the glaucoma suspects had VCDR $<0.6-0.7$.

A significant number of the patients, almost one-third with VCDR >0.85 , also had a moderate visual impairment to blindness ($P > 0.000$). Kass et al.⁽³²⁾ in

ocular hypertensive study, were able to pick 55% of glaucoma patients by optic disc assessment alone and another 10% by both optic disc and visual field defects. This underlies the importance of keen observation of the optic nerve head in follow-up of patients.

The VCDR asymmetry of ≥ 0.2 was seen in less than 1 in 4 individuals. This is not surprising since many had advanced to end-stage disease, when the difference in optic nerve head morphology had evened up.

Almost all the patients made a choice for medical treatment rather than surgery despite adequate counselling. The management of glaucoma in the

developing world, especially Africa, is usually a challenge. Even though surgery in the form of trabeculectomy with antimetabolites has been suggested as a first-line of treatment, due to poor compliance and cost of antiglaucoma medications, patients are often reluctant to choose the surgical option.

^(4,22,24,33) The short-term cost of surgery is likely to have influenced the uptake of surgery in this study as only a very few patients had surgery, even in the presence of skilled surgical workforce, with two consultant glaucoma subspecialists. Surgery outcome in advanced glaucoma may disappoint patients even when their IOP is controlled, since they do not experience any visual improvement. This may further deter others from choosing the surgical option of management. ⁽²⁸⁾

The topical anti-glaucoma medications most frequently used was the beta blocker, timolol. It is one of the lowest priced antiglaucoma drugs, and therefore, affordable for most patients. A very few patients were able to afford prostaglandin analogues, and these were those who had the National Health Insurance Scheme subsidized for their medications. Acetazolamide was added to lower the IOP in some patients with spiking intraocular pressure.

There was no significant difference in choice of treatment with regard to gender ($P=0.168$) and the state of visual acuity ($P=0.262$). One-tenth of patients had allergic reaction to the drugs and needed an added antiallergic medication.

An understanding of the goals of glaucoma management is essential, and information about this should be presented to patients in a way that helps them understand the benefits of treatment which might not be easily appreciated, especially in advanced disease.

Glaucoma screening programs in at-risk populations are crucial at all levels of health-care provision to facilitate early identification. The government and

nongovernmental Organizations need to put in place strategies to support individual's access to long-term treatment of this chronic, progressive condition with the aim of preserving and slowing down loss of vision.

Strength and Limitation

The strength of the study is that it has been carried out in a low-income area of Jos North Plateau State. This presents the challenges of early identification and management of glaucoma. As the first of its kind in this region, it provides valuable information to influence policy and future research.

The most important limitation is that the study is retrospective with potential for missing data. Secondly, it is a hospital-based study with a difficulty in generalizing the findings because hospital data are hardly truly reflective of the community burden of a disease especially in sub-Saharan Africa where access to healthcare is hampered by several adverse factors.

A key limitation of this study was the absence of essential diagnostic equipment, such as a Humphrey visual field analyzer, fundus (retinal) camera, pachymeter, and optical coherence tomography (OCT), which are critical for comprehensive glaucoma evaluation and monitoring. This limitation may have affected the precision of diagnosis, staging, and follow-up, thereby impacting optimal patient care.

From a community and public health perspective, inadequate diagnostic capacity can contribute to delayed detection, underdiagnosis, and progression to avoidable blindness within the population. This places a significant socioeconomic burden on patients, families, and the wider community, particularly in this resource-limited setting where access to specialized eye care is already constrained.

We therefore recommended that key stakeholders, including hospital management, government health authorities, and non-governmental organizations, should prioritize investment in essential ophthalmic equipment. Strengthening diagnostic infrastructure, alongside training of personnel and implementation of standardized glaucoma care protocols, which will enhance early detection, improve treatment outcomes, and ultimately reduce the burden of glaucoma-related visual impairment in this region.

CONCLUSION

The burden of glaucoma in this region is substantial, with one in three eyes already blind at presentation.

Primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) was the most common subtype. The majority of patients were managed with beta blockers.

Conflict of interest: The authors have declare none

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